

Supplementary Material S3.- Table 1.- Complete results of Generalized Linear Models explaining the variation in island species richness for the three main dung beetle groups using as predictors the twelve considered variables. Provided results for each explanatory variable considers both their linear (L) and quadratic (Q) functions against species richness as well as the sign of the relationship (negative or positive) and their coefficients and corresponding standard error (se). The percentage of explained deviance is calculated on a full model in which no predictors are included. All the values of the Wald statistics and their probability values are included..

	Full model	Number of published papers	PCA temperature component	PCA evapotranspiration component	PCA aridity component	years since first human colonization	Human density	Connection during LGM	Island geological origin	Area	Distance to mainland or large island	Nearest Continent	Maximum elevation	
Scarabaeinae	Deviance	1099.1	838.6	984.4	1028.9	1080.4	586.1	1085.9	1072.4	936.7	845.6	984.2	1058.2	978.9
	% Explained Deviance		23.7	10.4	6.4	1.7	46.7	1.2	2.4	14.8	23.1	10.4	3.7	10.9
	relationship		L (+)	Q (- -)	Q (+ +)	L (+)	Q (+ +)	Q (+ -)	L (+)	L (-)	Q (+ -)	Q (- +)	L (+)	L (+)
	coefficients		0.38	-4.56; -0.13	0.25; 0.05	0.01	0.87; 0.08	0.29; -0.06	0.39	-1.25	0.87; -0.08	-1.21; 0.26	0.71	0.32
	se		0.02	0.06; 0.05	0.04; 0.02	0.04	0.06; 0.02	0.09; 0.02	0.07	0.11	0.06; 0.01	0.16; 0.05	0.12	0.03
	Wald statistics		387.0	67.8; 7.4	44.8; 7.7	0.02	214.0; 21.2	10.1; 8.5	26.7	120.8	188.2; 89.5	53.0; 22.4	34.0	135.6
	P		<0.001	<0.001; 0.006	<0.001; 0.006	0.88	<0.001; <0.001	0.001; 0.003	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001; <0.001	<0.001; <0.001	<0.001	<0.001
Aphodiidae	Deviance	1576.6	822.2	1569.0	1503.7	1556.0	970.9	1458.1	1567.2	1537.6	934.2	1534.7	1556.1	1129.5
	% Explained Deviance		47.8	0.5	4.6	1.3	38.4	7.5	0.6	2.5	40.7	2.6	1.3	28.4
	relationship		L (+)	L (-)	Q (+ +)	L (+)	Q (+ +)	Q (+ -)	L (-)	L (-)	Q (+ -)	Q (+ -)	L (-)	L (+)
	coefficients		0.49	-0.09	0.12; 0.09	0.15	0.36; 0.08	0.80; -0.13	-0.20	-0.45	0.95; -0.08	0.32; -0.19	-0.34	0.49
	se		0.01	0.3	0.03; 0.01	0.04	0.04; 0.01	0.08; 0.02	0.07	0.07	0.05; 0.01	0.08; 0.03	0.07	0.02
	Wald statistics		1182.5	7.3	18.8; 53.2	19.4	84.7; 46.7	96.8; 44.8	9.2	36.3	348.6; 147.9	15.6; 28.8	21.7	563.9
	P		<0.001	0.01	<0.001; <0.001	<0.001	<0.001; <0.001	<0.001; <0.001	0.002	<0.001	<0.001; <0.001	<0.001; <0.001	<0.001	<0.001
Geotrupinae	Deviance	291.2	237.5	243.1	285.9	290.9	171.7	291.1	279.5	241.9	240.3	235.5	287.5	271.8
	% Explained Deviance		18.4	16.5	1.8	0.1	41.0	0.02	4.0	16.9	17.5	19.1	1.3	6.7
	relationship		L (+)	L (-)	L (+)	L (-)	L (+)	L (+)	L (+)	L (-)	L (+)	L (-)	L (+)	L (+)
	coefficients		0.35	-0.66	0.17	-0.04	0.66	0.02	0.51	-1.40	0.28	-1.70	0.39	0.27
	se		0.04	0.11	0.07	0.07	0.06	0.07	0.15	0.24	0.03	0.42	0.21	0.06
	Wald statistics		78.0	38.4	5.3	0.27	130.2	0.1	11.6	34.8	83.8	16.6	3.4	22.9
	P		<0.001	<0.001	0.02	0.60	<0.001	0.78	0.001	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	0.07	<0.001